

Preparation of metal-carbon composites from banana peel charcoal and metal salts for hydrogen storage by pyrolysis method

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Abstract : The metal-carbon composite materials from mixtures of banana peel charcoal and metal salts were studied. The synthesized materials are mixtures of banana peel charcoal (carbonized at 500 °C) and 5 wt% of metal salts [aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃), copper nitrate (Cu(NO₃)₂), zinc chloride (ZnCl₂), and magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄·7H₂O)]. The synthesis process of the metal-carbon composite materials is pyrolysis at 400, 500, 600 and 700 °C for 1 h in a closed crucible. The final products have been analyzed for percent yield and characterized using FT-IR, SEM and XRD. The hydrogen storage properties of pyrolysed products were also investigated. The percent yields of products decrease with increasing pyrolysis temperature from 400 °C to 700 °C. The FTIR spectra of products show small functional groups. The SEM microphotographs of products showed granular nanoparticles (θ = 58.61–400.5 nm) and nanofibers (θ = 62–261 nm, long = 200 μm). XRD patterns of products revealed graphitized and nano/amorphous carbon phases. The maximum hydrogen storage capacities of Cu-composites are between 6.06 wt% and 6.22 wt%.

Keywords : Carbon composite, banana peel charcoal, hydrogen storage, pyrolysis, metals salt.

Introduction

Metal-carbon composites have recently received significant amount attention as potential hydrogen storage materials, since nanosized metal particles seem to catalytically enhance hydrogen sorption at room temperature¹. The production of metal-carbon composite materials by adding metal to the carbon material for enhanced hydrogen storage, as been reported, for example, inclusion of Mg²⁻⁴, Pd^{5,6}, Li, Na, Ca⁴, Zr⁷, Ag⁸, Ni³ and V⁶. Many types of carbon materials were used in the preparation of composites such as graphite^{2,9}, carbon nanotubes⁸⁻¹⁰, single walled nanotubes¹¹, carbon black^{7,9}, carbon nanofibres, multi-walled carbon nanotubes^{6,12}, nanocarbon⁴, and activated carbon¹³. It was found that the hydrogen storage capacity in metal-carbon composites was higher than 5 wt%. For example, in bulk specimens of Mg – 23.5 wt% Ni/CNTs composites a concentration of hydrogen as high as 6.1 wt% has been obtained by the described hydrogenation process³. Addition of metal as a metal hydride to the carbon materials enhances the performance of the gas storage vessel¹⁴.

This project studied the preparation of metal-carbon composites from the mixtures of banana peel charcoal

and metal salts of Al, Cu, Zn, or Mg using a pyrolysis method, which has been used before for the pyrolysis of kapok fiber¹⁵. The influences of pyrolysis temperature and different type of metal salts on the morphology of metal-carbon composite materials were studied by FT-IR, XRD and SEM. The hydrogen storage properties of the synthesized metal-carbon composite materials were explored as well.

Materials and methods :

Sample preparation :

Carbonization of banana peel :

Banana peels were obtained from a dried waste banana plant in Phitsanulok, Thailand. The banana peels were sun dried and then oven dried for 6 h. Approximately 20 g of the banana peels were carbonized at 500 °C for 1 h. After that, the residue was cooled to room temperature. The dried banana peel charcoals were kept in a desiccator.

Metal-carbon composites preparation :

Ten grams of mixed banana peel charcoal and 5 wt% of Al₂O₃, 5 wt% Cu(NO₃)₂, 5 wt% ZnCl₂, or 5 wt% MgSO₄·7H₂O were placed in a closed crucible (size 105/

73, 102/70). The samples were pyrolysed at 400, 500, 600 and 700 °C in an electric furnace (Fisher Scientific Isotemp® Muffle Furnace). The temperature was increased with a rate of 15 °C/min up to the desired temperature and kept constant for 1 h. In the last step, the pyrolysis products were cooled to room temperature. The final products were kept in the desiccator.

Analysis and characterization :

Approximate analysis of banana peel :

Fixed carbon, ash content, and volatile matter content of banana peel were analyzed by methods of ASTM D 3172-89¹⁶, ASTM D 2866-94¹⁷ and ASTM D 5832-95¹⁸, respectively. The pyrolysed products were analyzed for percent yield and characterized by a Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FTIR, Spectrum GX, Perkin-Elmer), X-ray Diffractometer (XRD, PW 3040/60, X'Pert Pro MPD), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM/EDS, LEO 1455 VP).

Hydrogen storage experiments :

Hydrogen storage experiments were performed in a conventional static volumetric adsorption apparatus, which can be operated at hydrogen pressures of up to 1.5 bar¹⁹.

Results and discussion

Percent yield and approximate analysis :

The approximate composition of the banana peel is 37.70% of fixed carbon, 52.00% of volatile matter and 10.30% of ash. Given the amount of ash content, it was concluded that the banana peel is a highly mineral. This result is in agreement with the findings reported by Emaga *et al.*²⁰ who found high contents of potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium, iron, zinc, manganese and copper in banana peel. Furthermore, high amounts of volatile matter in banana peel consisting of cellulose, wax, carbohydrate or polysaccharide, lignin, and lignocellulose²¹ were removed by pyrolysis. The functional groups of organic compounds were decomposed by thermal decomposition reaction. Compounds containing carbon as a main component of the banana peels were reduced to carbon in the form of fixed carbon. The banana peels with high carbon content can be considered precursors in the production of carbon.

Table 1 presents percent yield of the metal-banana peel carbon composites. It can be seen that the yield de-

Table 1. Percent yield of metal-carbon composites obtained by pyrolysis at temperatures from 400 to 700 °C

Composite types	% yield of composites by pyrolysis at			
	400 °C	500 °C	600 °C	700 °C
Al-banana peel carbon composite	96.68	92.21	91.55	90.06
Cu-banana peel carbon composite	37.89	30.19	25.81	17.11
Mg-banana peel carbon composite	54.61	53.03	52.41	20.16
Zn-banana peel carbon composite	97.99	93.44	92.29	86.51

creases with increasing pyrolysis temperature in the range from 400 to 700 °C. This is in line with recent publications¹⁵, which concluded that the amount of decomposition of samples depended on the oxidizing strength of the metal salt. The sequence of oxidizing power of metal salts is $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 < \text{ZnCl}_2 < \text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} < \text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. The percent yield of isolated composite by mixing Al_2O_3 or ZnCl_2 with banana peels was relatively high and almost constant in the pyrolysis temperature range from 400 to 700 °C. This indicates that the initial substances were oxidized at a small scale. This phenomenon can be explained by the fact that the Al_2O_3 exhibits low oxidizing power at temperatures between 300 °C and 900 °C, where the amorphous alumina layers become metastable as the thickness exceeds a critical value²². In case of ZnCl_2 , the micropores on the carbon²³, which has a little oxidation, were increased. In the case of composite preparation with $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the percent yield was very low. In this case, both SO_4^{2-} and Mg^{2+} are highly effective for oxidation²⁴. The percent yields, which were in the range of 54.61–52.41% for temperatures from 400 to 600 °C, dropped to 20.16% at 700 °C. The lowest percent yield was observed for composites prepared using $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ as the metal salt. In this case the yield decreased gradually from 400 to 700 °C. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is a highly oxidizing agent²⁵. Thus, the decomposition of carbon material mixed with $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is the highest.

FT-IR analysis :

The FT-IR spectra of aluminium-banana peel charcoal composite materials are shown in Fig. 1. All composites displayed the following bands : a broad band at 3435 cm^{-1} and a weak band at $1642\text{--}1659 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Both bands are due to vibrations of O-H groups, corresponding to the stretching and bending vibrations²⁶ of surface hydroxylic groups and chemisorbed water²⁷. The asym-

Fig. 1. FTIR transmission spectra of aluminium-banana peel charcoal composites obtained by pyrolysis at 400 °C (AB1), 500 °C (AB2), 600 °C (AB3) and 700 °C (AB4).

metric band at lower wave numbers indicates presence of strong hydrogen bonds between surface functional groups and adsorbed water molecules. The adsorbed water on the surface of activated carbons participated in specific (hydrogen bonds, chemisorption due to surface oxides hydration) and non-specific interactions (physical adsorption)²⁸. The intensity of these bands decreased with increasing pyrolysis temperature. This means that the amount of OH surface functional groups was reduced when the sample was treated at higher temperatures. In addition, all of the aluminium carbon composites showed IR peaks at 1408–1418 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to C=O groups.

The C=O groups were formed by oxidation during the pyrolysis process²⁸. A broad peak at 819 cm^{-1} was observed as well. This peak may be attributed to esters, such as $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO-O-}$, as well as cyclic C-O-C groups conjugated with carbon-carbon double bonds (C=C-O-C) in olefinic or aromatic structures, which represent major components in lignocellulosic material, e.g. $-\text{OCH}_3$ in ethers²⁹. The weak peak at 579 cm^{-1} of the aluminium-carbon composites for all of the pyrolysis temperatures associated with ν O-H in OH groups, where it seems non-free and involved in hydrogen bonds²⁹.

For FTIR spectra of the copper-banana peel charcoal composites, all spectra were similar to the spectra in Fig. 1. However, the OH stretching and bending around 3400 cm^{-1} and 1650 cm^{-1} were decreased in intensity due to an increase in the pyrolysis temperature. This observation indicates that hydrogen bonding is much less preva-

lent at higher temperatures. There were also prominent peaks at 1384 cm^{-1} of δ O-H vibrations and ν C=O vibrations²⁹, which are observed at all temperatures. Peaks around 1007–1032 cm^{-1} were expected to be C-O or C-O-C stretching vibrations³⁰. Finally, a peak at 526 cm^{-1} may be attributed to aliphatic C-H vibrations³¹.

FTIR spectra of the magnesium-banana peel charcoal composite materials contain broad and weak peaks at 3400 cm^{-1} (O-H group stretching) and a very weak peak at 1655 cm^{-1} . It was found that the intensity of the spectrum decreases with increasing pyrolysis temperature. The peak at 1384 cm^{-1} (δ O-H vibrations) also disappeared. This indicates that the OH groups were eliminated. This phenomenon demonstrates that MgSO_4 is a good dehydrating agent. In contrast, the intensity of the peaks at 1100 cm^{-1} (C-O or C-O-C stretching vibrations) and 617 cm^{-1} (C-C stretching vibrations) increased with increasing pyrolysis temperature. It has been shown that oxidation occurred to a higher extent when the pyrolysis temperature increases. Meanwhile, other functional groups were decomposed. The very small peaks at about 419–427 cm^{-1} in spectrum may be attributed to aliphatic C-H vibrations³¹.

FTIR spectra of zinc-banana peel charcoal composite materials are shown that there are relatively sharp peaks at 3550 cm^{-1} and 1620 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching and bending). The maximum transmittance of hydrogen-bonded O-H stretching is shifted to higher wave numbers in comparison to other composites. This indicates that the main O-H stretching is due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding with increased Zn content. There was also a very weak peak at 525 cm^{-1} (C-C stretching vibrations). The low number of peaks in these composite material's spectra suggest that ZnCl_2 acts as a good decomposing agent for surface functional groups.

XRD analysis :

The XRD spectra of the aluminium-banana peel charcoal composites (Fig. 2) show a peaks at 38° and 68°, which corresponds to poorly crystallized Al_2O_3 ³². From the spectra we can see that the composites are amorphous, and that the composites are mainly carbon. The results of XRD are consistent with the percent yields shown in Table 1 and the FTIR spectra (Fig. 1), which show low decomposition of initial samples.

Fig. 3 displays the XRD spectra of copper-banana peel charcoal composites. There are dominant peaks at

Fig. 2. X-Ray powder diffraction spectra of aluminium-banana peel charcoal composites obtained by pyrolysis at 400 °C (AB1), 500 °C (AB2), 600 °C (AB3) and 700 °C (AB4).

Fig. 3. X-Ray powder diffraction spectra of copper-banana peel charcoal composites obtained by pyrolysis at 400 °C (CB1), 500 °C (CB2), 600 °C (CB3) and 700 °C (CB4).

35°, 36° and 39° in all spectra, which show the characteristics of CuO ³³. This indicates that the oxidizing power of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is very high. This is due to the decomposition of nitrate ions (NO_3^-) to NO_x . It reveals that nitrate ions are thermally removed and the salt (CuNO_3) is converted to the metal (Cu) or metal oxide (Cu_2O , CuO)³⁴. The $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ decomposition results in an increasing amount of Cu, CuO , or Cu_2O in the composition of the composite. In addition, these spectra also show that the pyrolysed product is crystalline. This is consistent with the observed percent yield (Table 1) and FTIR spectra (Fig. 2), which show high degree of decomposition.

For XRD spectra of magnesium-banana peel charcoal composite materials, the degree of crystallinity of the composites increases with increasing pyrolysis temperature in the range from 400 °C to 600 °C. The crystalline

product was obtained using pyrolysis temperature of 700 °C. This crystalline product was confirmed by the appearance of dominant peaks at 1150 cm^{-1} and 879.33 cm^{-1} in FTIR spectra of magnesium-banana peel charcoal composite materials.

XRD spectra of the zinc-banana peel charcoal composites are displayed that the degree of crystallinity of the composites increased with increasing temperature in the range of 400 °C to 700 °C. The weak peaks at about 32° and 38° were the characteristic peaks of a Zn compound³⁵.

SEM analysis :

SEM images of aluminium-banana peel charcoal composite materials obtained at pyrolysis temperatures from 400 °C to 700 °C (Fig. 4) show granular particles (diameter = 129.5–150 nm) and nanofibers (diameter = 62–261 nm, length = 200 μm). Figs. 4a and 4b are SEM images of aluminium-banana peel charcoal composites with pyrolysis performed at 400 and 500 °C. The composite has a rough surface covering some of the fibers and the pellets. Composites obtained at pyrolysis at temperatures of 600 and 700 °C (Figs. 4c and d) contain a large number of pellet particles on their surface. This phenomenon indicates that the composite material forms more easily at higher temperatures.

In Fig. 5 SEM images of copper-banana peel charcoal composite with pyrolysis at 400–700 °C are shown. A high number of pellet crystals with a diameter of 54–195 nm was observed on the surfaces of these products. These pellets were expected to be crystalline form of a Cu compound. This result indicates that a large amount of the substrate was degraded (according to Table 1). This results in a higher proportion of crystalline material (consistent with the crystalline phase which found in the XRD spectra in Fig. 3). Additionally, striped pores were found on the surfaces of the composite materials.

The surfaces of the magnesium-banana peel charcoal composites obtained at pyrolysis temperatures of 400–700 °C have different size (diameters vary from 93.53 to 400.5 nm) of pellet particles with a relatively higher-ordered structure than that for the copper-banana peel charcoal composite. Some fibers were also found in the

Fig. 4. SEM images of aluminium-banana peel charcoal composites obtained by pyrolysis at 400 °C (a), 500 °C (b), 600 °C (c) and 700 °C (d).

Fig. 5. SEM images of copper-banana peel charcoal composites obtained by pyrolysis at 400 °C (a), 500 °C (b), 600 °C (c) and 700 °C (d).

composite materials, especially the product of pyrolysis at 700 °C.

The surfaces of the zinc-banana peel charcoal composites obtained at temperatures of 400–700 °C have large amounts of very small particles with a diameter of 58.61–241.2 nm. The composite surfaces are rough and show edge lines. The surface of the product composite obtained at 700 °C has fewer pellet particles and a thin layer of overlapping lines.

Hydrogen storage :

The results for hydrogen storage analysis of the composites obtained by pyrolysis at 400–700 °C are presented in Table 2. The metal salt and the temperature of pyrolysis affect the hydrogen storage capacity for different composites. The results revealed that the hydrogen storage

Table 2. Hydrogen storage capacity of composites

Composite type	Hydrogen storage (wt%)
Al-banana peel charcoal composite-400 °C	2.36
Al-banana peel charcoal composite-500 °C	3.78
Al-banana peel charcoal composite-600 °C	3.86
Al-banana peel charcoal composite-700 °C	3.85
Cu-banana peel charcoal composite-400 °C	5.24
Cu-banana peel charcoal composite-500 °C	6.06
Cu-banana peel charcoal composite-600 °C	6.22
Cu-banana peel charcoal composite-700 °C	6.15
Mg-banana peel charcoal composite-400 °C	3.50
Mg-banana peel charcoal composite-500 °C	4.01
Mg-banana peel charcoal composite-600 °C	4.43
Mg-banana peel charcoal composite-700 °C	4.44
Zn-banana peel charcoal composite-400 °C	0.34
Zn-banana peel charcoal composite-500 °C	0.39
Zn-banana peel charcoal composite-600 °C	0.35
Zn-banana peel charcoal composite-700 °C	0.39

capacity of all composites increased with increasing pyrolysis temperature from 400 to 700 °C. This is due to increased porosity and increased content of metals achieved with increasing pyrolysis temperature. The effect of metal salts on the hydrogen storage capacity of composite products obtained at the same pyrolysis temperature can be summarized in the following order of hydrogen storage capacity : Cu-banana peel charcoal composite > Mg-

banana peel charcoal composite > Al-banana peel charcoal composite > Zn-banana peel charcoal composite. The Zn-banana peel charcoal composite has a relatively low hydrogen storage capacity, because it is rather sensitive to humidity³⁶. This result is supported by the FTIR spectra of zinc-banana peel charcoal shown in which the main features are sharp peaks of O-H stretching and bending. In addition, lower textural properties of the composite resulted in the low hydrogen affinity to Zn³⁷. The hydrogen storage capacity of Cu-banana peel charcoal composite was close to the standard (6.5% wt of the US Department of Energy)¹⁴. This result is consistent with the report of Park *et al.*³⁸. In this case, all of the hydrogen molecules associate on Cu surfaces, and then the fully covered Cu surface transfer hydrogen atoms into the carbon structure³⁸. This could be due to the smaller particle size of the Cu composites (Fig. 5), which results in higher surface area than for other composites. The Cu composite therefore has a higher absorption capacity. Hydrogen storage capacity of Mg-banana peel charcoal composite and Al-banana peel charcoal composite was close to the report of Shindo *et al.*³⁹ using carbon, graphite, activated carbon fiber, and activated carbon powder. This can be explained by hydrogen uptake through the bonding of H⁺ at oxygen sites and H⁻ at oxygen vacancies. However, the H of the OH group cannot dissociate easily as H⁻ due to the absence of bond forming⁴⁰.

Conclusions

In this study, the FTIR results revealed that the strength of the breakdown of banana peel charcoals by metal salts ranges in the following order of Al₂O₃ < ZnCl₂ < MgSO₄·7H₂O < Cu(NO₃)₂, which corresponds to the oxidizing power of the four metal salts. The FT-IR spectra of products showed presence of small functional groups, especially in Zn-carbon composites. The XRD patterns of the products revealed the presence of graphitized carbon and nano/amorphous particles. The degree of crystallinity of the composites increased with increasing pyrolysis temperature. The SEM microphotographs of products showed the existence of granular particles (θ = 58.61–400.5 nm) and nanofibers (θ = 62–261 nm, long = 200 μm). The preparation of carbon composite at 700 °C

gave higher amount of fibers and granular particles than the preparation at 400–600 °C. Finally, the hydrogen storage capacity of all composites increased with increasing pyrolysis temperature. The hydrogen storage capacity of Cu-composites is between 6.06 wt% and 6.22 wt%, which is close to the standard of the US Department of Energy.

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References

1. D. Giasafaki, A. Bourlinos, G. Charalambopoulou, A. Stubos and T. H. Steriotis, *Micropor. Mesopor. Mat.*, 2012, **74**, 154.
2. H. Imamura, S. Tabata, N. Shigetomi, Y. Takesue and Y. Sakata, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2002, **579**, 330.
3. R. Schaller, D. Maria, S. Marques dos Santos, I. Tkalceca and E. Carreño-Morelli, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (A)*, 2009, **147**, 521.
4. H. Miyaoka, T. Ichikawa, S. Isobe and H. Fujii, *Physica (B)*, 2006, **51**, 383.
5. P. Ndungu, A. Nechaev, L. Khotseng, N. Onyegebule, W. Davids, R. Mohammed, G. Vaivars, B. Bladegroen and V. Linkov, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energ.*, 2008, **33**, 3102.
6. Y. Suttisawat, P. Rangsunvigit, B. Kitiyanan, M. Williams, P. Ndungu, M. V. Lototsky, A. Nechaev, V. Linkov and S. Kulprathipanja, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energ.*, 2009, **34**, 6669.
7. F. Mulana, N. Nishimiya, H. Saito, A. Matsumoto and K. Tsutsumi, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2004, **372**, 243.
8. S. Rather, M. Naik and S. W. Hwang, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2009, **475**, L17.
9. Z. G. Huang, Z. P. Guo, A. Calka, D. Wexler and H. K. Liu, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2007, **427**, 94.
10. D. Chena, L. Chena, S. Liua, C. X. Mab, D. M. Chena and L. B. Wang, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2004, **372**, 231.
11. C. Z. Wu, P. Wang, X. Yaob, C. Liua, D. M. Chen, G. Q. Lub and H. W. Cheng, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2006, **420**, 278.
12. M. A. Lillo-Rodenas, Z. X. Guo, K. F. Aguey-Zinsou, D. Carzorra-Amoros and A. Linares-Solano, *Carbon*, 2008, **46**, 126.
13. J. W. H. Smith, P. Westreich, A. J. Smith, H. Fortier, L. M. Croll, J. S. Reynolds and J. R. Dahn, *J. Colloid. Interf. Sci.*, 2010, **341**, 162.
14. L. L. Vasiliev and L. E. Kanonchik, *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 2010, **65**, 2586.
15. W. Singse, S. Mopoung and A. Sirikulajorn, *Sci. Res. Essays.*, 2012, **7**, 1592.
16. American Standard of Testing Material, "Standard Test Method for Fixed Carbon in Activate Carbon", ASTM D, 1994, pp. 3172-3189.
17. American Standard of Testing Material, "Standard Test Method for Total Ash Content of Activate Carbon", ASTM D, 1996, pp. 2866-2894.
18. American Standard of Testing Material, "Standard Test Method for Volatile Matter Content of Activate Carbon", ASTM D, 1996, pp. 5832-5895.
19. C. Souvakon, A. Vorasingha, S. Mopoung and A. Vongkumhae, *Int. J. Phys. Sci.*, 2011, **6**, 1477.
20. T. H. Emaga, R. H. Andrianaivo, B. Wathelet, J. T. Tchango and M. Paquot, *Food Chem.*, 2007, **103**, 590.
21. T. T. Lim and X. Huang, *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 2007, **26**, 125.
22. M. A. Trunov, M. Schoenitz, X. Zhu and E. L. Dreizin, *Combust. Flame.*, 2005, **140**, 310.
23. J. Cheng, L. Yang, L. Dong, X. Long and W. Yuan, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 2012, **18**, 1628.
24. N. Tang, Y. Liu, H. Wang, L. Xiao and Z. Wu, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2010, **160**, 145.
25. J. W. Moore, C. L. Stanitski and P. C. Jurs, "Principles of chemistry : The molecular science", Books/Cole, Cengage Learning, Belmont, USA, 2010, pp. A.32-34.
26. J. Chłopek, A. Morawska-Chochół and C. Paluszkievicz, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2008, **875**, 101.
27. M. Pakua, M. Walczyk, S. Biniak and A. Świątkowski, *Chemosphere*, 2007, **69**, 209.
28. S. Shin, J. Jang, S. H. Yoon and I. Mochida, *Carbon*, 1997, **35**, 1739.
29. A. N. A. El-Hendawy, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrol.*, 2006, **75**, 159.
30. E. Pamuła, M. Błaewicz, C. Paluszkievicz and P. Dobrzyński, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2001, **596**, 69.
31. B. S. Girgis, E. Smith, M. M. Louis and A. N. A. El-Hendawy, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrol.*, 2009, **86**, 180.
32. R. Birjega, S. I. Vizireanu, G. Dinescu, L. C. Nistor and R. Ganea, *Superlattice. Microst.*, 2009, **46**, 97.
33. L. Eswaramoorthi, V. Sundaramurthy and A. K.

- Dalai, *Appl. Catal. (A) : Gen.*, 2006, **313**, 22.
34. X. Hu, L. Lei, H. P. Chu and P. L. Yue, *Carbon*, 1999, **37**, 631.
35. R. Wang, D. Song, W. Liu and X. He, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2010, **257**, 203.
36. S. M. Luzan, H. Jung, H. Chun and A. V. Talyzin, *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energ.*, 2009, **34**, 9754.
37. J. A. Botas, G. Calleja, M. Sánchez-Sánchez and M. G. Orcajo, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energ.*, 2011, **36**, 10834.
38. S. J. Park, B. J. Kim, Y. S. Lee and M. J. Cho, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energ.*, 2008, **33**, 1706.
39. K. Shindo, T. Kondo and Y. Sakurai, *J. Alloy. Comp.*, 2004, **372**, 201.
40. Z. Yaakob, D. J. Khadem, S. Shahgaldi, W. R. W. Daud and S. M. Tasirin, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energ.*, 2012, **37**, 8388.